

THE ANALYSIS OF STUDENTS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS TEACHER'S PRESENCE IN ONLINE AND OFFLINE LESSONS (BASED ON QUESTIONNAIRE)

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ABSTRACT

Significant changes in science and technology has facilitated the improvement of teaching as well as learning. Teacher's presence is considered as one of the most crucial components of successful learning environment, nevertheless, student's centered approach is acknowledged by plethora of specialists. The current work scrutinizes the reaction of freshmen to teacher's presence in Reading and Writing classes in language-specialized university. The study is based on the questionnaire in which about 50 students have participated. The research depends on both quantitative and comparative approaches to identify student's real opinion about teacher's presence. This is applicable because presence may contribute to teachers' reflection-in-action and their ability to reply to classroom situations.

Introduction

Teacher's presence in the classroom consists of the monitoring the class, the holding the students' attention and focus, the creation of facilitation for pupils. This process commences with planning of the lesson until delivering it successfully. The teacher's presence guarantees the fulfillment of the objectives of each lesson. Teacher's presence is a topic which is most discussed and not well-researched in terms of students' reaction towards it. This research is aimed at identifying student's reaction to teacher's presence through some questions. The questions are composed differently: multiple choice questions and short-answer questions

enable students to choose one or more opinions as well as they are able to express their ideas to the given questions with concise comments or opinions.

Literature review and methodology

Initially, the notion "presence" in teaching was described in a various way by great number of specialists and scholars. Greene, Tremmel and Rud suggested that an important factor of presence is being present for oneself. Teaching requires connecting with students and their learning, and the health of that correlation is nurtured or jeopardized by the teacher's relationship to herself. Another source indicates that teacher's presence is strongly connected to the word "alive". He

points out that The teacher must ‘give full time and attention to observation and interpretation of the pupils’ intellectual reactions.

Early researches and surveys suggest that rapport between teacher and student is a cornerstone in student achievement, motivation and engagement and in their capacity to trust what they know. Carol R. Rodgers & Miriam B. Raider-Roth in their article “Presence in teaching” state that ‘presence’—a state of alert awareness, receptivity and connectedness to the mental, emotional and physical workings of both the individual and the group in the context of their learning environments and the ability to respond with a considered and compassionate best next step. In addition, they point out that teaching and learning should consist of

only acquisition and assessment, but it must be based on self-knowledge, trust, relationship and compassion.

One of the researches elaborates that teaching presence is “the design, facilitation, and direction of cognitive and social processes for the purpose of realizing personally meaningful and educationally worthwhile learning outcomes”. Another source (Baker and Taylor) identifies that teachers are perceived as “present” in the online course when “visible” to the students. In other words, the students know the teachers are attending to and participating in the class. The following figure is called Community of Inquiry (CoI) Framework which was developed by Garrison, Anderson, and Archer in 2000.

Figure 1. Community of Inquiry (CoI) Framework

Nevertheless, the CoI model also consists of social presence and cognitive presence (Figure 1), supporters of model believe

that teaching presence plays a regulatory and mediating role, which “ brings all the elements of a community of inquiry

together in a balanced and functional relationship congruent with the intended outcomes and the needs and capabilities of the learners". All in all, teaching presence serves as a bridge between a teacher and learner which creates an amazing learning environment and it makes the learning process more successful and fun.

The research was based on a questionnaire in which qualitative and comparative methods to analyze students' reaction towards teacher's presence in the classroom. The questions in the questionnaire were multiple-choice and short-answer questions. The replies of students to multiple-choice questions are presented with the help of diagram and pie chart while responses to short answer questions are given in the form of summary. The participants of the research are 50 freshmen students who study at

language-specialized university (Uzbekistan State World Languages University). They are given enough time to fill the table and share what they have experienced with teacher's presence during whole year. They have been allowed to answer anonymously which let students respond freely without thinking they may be caught if they have written negative comments to the given questions.

Results and discussions

The first question was aimed at identifying the satisfaction of students' to teacher's presence in Reading and Writing offline lessons. The results show that more than 95 % students indicated that they were satisfied with the teacher's presence while 2% of student did not have satisfaction. The another alternative "I don't know" was not chosen by anyone.

Fig. 1. Are you satisfied with your teachers' offline lessons?

The next question was quite similar to the first question, but emphasis was given to detecting students' approval of online lessons. The results were almost the

same. Almost all students (98%) were satisfied with teacher's presence in online lessons while only 2 % of students answered negatively to the given question.

Fig. 2. Are you satisfied with your teachers' online lessons?

The next question touches upon the assessment of students. The question was based on whether students considered that teachers had assessed them fairly or they did not have any idea about this process. The results show that more than 86%

agreed that assessment was done fairly while 9.8 % of students did not have any clue about this issue. The rest of the students noted that assessment was not fair.

Fig. 3. Do you think that you have been assessed fairly?

Another question was made to reveal what sorts of changes are necessary in these teachers' Reading and Writing lessons. 27 students out of 51 would like teachers to change the way of punishing

their students like subtraction of points for late submission and so on. Other higher percentages were taken by alteration of teacher's demanding character and honesty.

Fig. 4. What do you think that teachers should change in their lessons?

The next question was intended to see students' preferences of what they liked most in their teachers' lessons. The

following diagram shows what they liked most. In this question, students were permitted to choose more than one option.

Fig. 5. What did you like most in your teachers' lessons?

The next two questions were short-answer questions, and they were designed to get students' suggestions to improve teachers' presence in the classroom and their overall feedback related to the entire course and teachers.

Most of the suggestions were related to interaction mode between students. They wanted to work mostly in pairs and groups to develop their

collaborative and team working skills. In addition, students would like to have more interactive and physical activities to improve focus and concentration.

Major number of students expressed positive feedback towards Reading and Writing lessons during whole year. Some students just wrote very precise replies like "Everything was ok", "Good" and so on.

To analyze the results, nearly each student was satisfied with teacher's presence in online and offline lessons. However, minority of students did not have any idea about whether the teachers had assessed them fairly or not. Regarding to comments by students to have suggestions for Reading and Writing lessons, the messages were positive and they expressed their ideas of working more with pairs and groupmates than individual tasks. Furthermore, since they have a sedentary lifestyle, they would like to do some interactive and educational games which make them be physically active. The positive comments of students prove that teacher's presence was well-organized during Reading and Writing lessons. There was no or less problems germane to lesson planning and process. Moreover, students admitted that they noticed some improvements in their reading and writing skills.

Conclusion

Teacher's presence is considered as one of the most significant milestones of teaching and learning. Correctly planned and processed teacher's presence in the

classroom guarantees the success of learning process. Teaching process is one of the integral parts of education experience. The term "teacher's presence" can be called as "teaching presence" and it has been defined differently by plethora of specialists and scientists. The research was created to analyze students' reaction towards teacher's presence in online and offline lessons. Overall, all the results were positive: students were satisfied with both online and offline lessons. However, they have some doubts about whether they have been assessed fairly or not which teachers would like to make sure that students will be informed about assessment and how it is being held in advance next year. According to the results of the research, most of the suggestions were directed to changing the way of teachers' punishments when they are late or when they have not done homework on time. All in all, the research shows that teaching presence existed in target classroom. At the same time, some drawbacks were found, but they are planned to be tackled in upcoming semester.

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